

Trifluorenyl lanthanides: Anhydrous trichloride (1 mol) of Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Gd, Dy and Sm were treated with potassium fluorenyl (3 mol) in THF. The other operations were similar as described in case of indenyl complexes. Lanthanides, carbon and hydrogen were estimated by standard methods (Table 1). Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 137 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The preparation of the triindenyl and trifluorenyl complexes of lanthanides could be represented by the following equations,

where, Ln = lanthanide ion and R = indenyl (C_9H_7) or fluorenyl (C_{13}H_9) group. The compounds were stable in dry and inert atmosphere and usually decomposed on heating. These were soluble in polar solvents like acetone tetrahydrofuran and alcohols but insoluble in non-polar solvents like benzene, xylene, toluene and carbontetrachloride.

Infrared spectra:

Indenyl group: The presence of indenyl group in the triindenyl complexes of Sc, Y, Ce, Pr and Nd has been inferred from the presence of ir bands both due to cyclopentadienyl as well as phenyl groups. $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$ and C—H out-of-plane bending bands were observed at 3100–2900, 1460 and 820 cm^{-1} , respectively. The 1140 and 1020 cm^{-1} bands were due to deformation vibrations of ring protons⁵. In addition, the peaks at 1380 (C—H stretching), 1700–1750 (C—C stretching) and 750 cm^{-1} (C—H out-of-plane bending vibrations) are due to phenyl group in indene. The band at 720 cm^{-1} was due to methylene rocking vibration. Indene itself absorbs at 700 cm^{-1} ⁶.

Fluorenyl group: The ir spectra of trifluorenyl lanthanides (Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd and Dy) are strikingly similar to the spectra of fluorene except for the absence or lowering in the intensities of the peaks associated with the methylene group at 2930, 1400, 1298, 1190, 950, 867, 853 cm^{-1} ⁶, whereas other peaks could be assigned as follows: 3100 and 2930 (C—H stretching), 1750–1550 (C—C stretching), 1000 cm^{-1} (C—H in-plane bending) and 750 cm^{-1} (C—H out-of-plane bending). The peak at 700 cm^{-1} may be due to the methylene rocking vibration (fluorene itself absorbs at 692 cm^{-1})⁶.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of the Complexation of Nickel(II) with DL-2-Aminobutanedicarboxylic Acid

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Manuscript received 12 January 1987, revised 24 June 1987, accepted 23 July 1987

EARLIER investigations¹⁻⁴ deal with complexation of Ni^{II} with DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid only at 25°. In the present investigation, it is found that $k_1=0$ at 25° and increased with the increase in temperature, as reported by Cassatt and Wilkins¹. Complexation of Ni^{II} with DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid was investigated in the pH range 6.25–7.41, at 25–40 ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) and at ionic strength 0.3M NaNO_3 .

Experimental

DL-2-Aminobutanedicarboxylic acid (B.D.H.), 2,6-lutidine (Merck-Schuchardt), NaNO_3 and bromothymol blue (AnalaR) were used. Solution of Ni^{II} ($\sim 10^{-5}M$) was prepared from $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck). Double-distilled water was used in the preparation of all solutions. Ionic strength of all reaction mixtures was adjusted to 0.3M (NaNO_3). Freshly prepared solution of DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid ($1.21 \times 10^{-3}M$) was used. A Radiometer pHM 26 pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Kinetic study was made using Aminco Morrow stopped flow spectrophotometer. The driving syringes and reaction chamber were thermostated at the desired temperatures with a circulating type Prufgerat NBE thermostat. Bromothymol blue ($\sim 10^{-5}M$) was added to DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid solution. Both metal and ligand were buffered with 0.05M 2,6-lutidine and the initial pH of the solutions containing metal and ligand were kept constant. Slight change in the pH (of the order of 0.05) was observed after mixing and the reported values are those of the reaction mixtures.

All the reactions were followed spectrophotometrically at 620 nm to monitor the change in absorbance with time. For every set, 10–15 runs were made and pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the plot of $\log \Delta V$ vs time.

Blank experiment in which Ni^{II} ions were mixed with buffer and indicator showed no change in absorbance.

Results and Discussion

Edsall and Blanchard⁵ have shown that the predominant form of DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid (ADA) is

and this becomes more significant in the pH range 6.00–7.00^{1,4,6}. The stopped flow trace indicated the occurrence of only one reaction which followed the overall differential rate equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Ni}^{2+}] \\ &= -\frac{d}{dt} [\text{ADA}] \\ &= k_{\text{obs}} [\text{ADA}] [\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}] \\ &= k'_{\text{obs}} [\text{ADA}] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Linear plots of log ΔV vs time confirm the above view. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k'obs) and second order rate constants (kobs = k'obs/[Ni^{II}]) calculated from such plots are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FIRST AND SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR COMPLEXING OF Ni^{II} BY DL-2-AMINOBUTANEDICARBOXYLIC ACID AT DIFFERENT pH'S AND AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

[DL-2-Aminobutanedicarboxylic acid] = 1.21 × 10⁻³ M, I = 0.3 M NaNO₃

[Ni ^{II}] × 10 ³ M	Temp. °C	pH	k'obs × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	kobs × 10 ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1.21	25	6.27	15.06	1.26
1.21	25	6.49	19.25	1.59
1.21	25	6.74	40.76	3.37
1.21	25	7.03	99.00	8.18
1.32	25	7.26	185.89	14.91
1.32	25	7.41	209.98	15.90
1.21	30	6.29	20.38	1.68
1.21	30	6.49	31.50	2.60
1.21	30	6.74	69.30	5.73
1.21	30	7.00	126.00	10.41
1.21	30	7.22	173.25	14.31
1.21	30	7.41	288.75	23.86
1.25	35	6.25	35.75	2.86
1.25	35	6.44	51.12	4.09
1.25	35	6.70	89.50	7.16
1.25	35	7.03	178.87	14.31
1.45	35	7.19	296.52	20.45
1.45	35	7.36	415.13	28.63
1.21	40	6.29	49.49	4.09
1.21	40	6.41	69.21	5.72
1.21	40	6.72	126.00	10.41
1.32	40	7.04	314.95	23.86
1.32	40	7.20	377.92	28.63
1.32	40	7.36	539.88	40.90

The reaction of Ni^{II} with DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid may be as follows,

This leads⁴ to

$$k_{\text{obs}} \cdot \frac{K_a + [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} = k_1 + \frac{k_2 K_a}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (5)$$

Plots of kobs · {Ka + [H⁺]}/[H⁺] vs [H⁺]⁻¹ at the temperatures studied were linear (Fig 1). Knowing Ka = 2.51 × 10⁻¹⁰ M at 25°, the values of Ka are obtained at other temperatures using the relation,

$$\text{p}K_a = \frac{\Delta H_a \cdot (T_2 - T_1)}{4.6 T_2 \cdot T_1} + \text{p}K_a^{25^\circ} \quad (6)$$

Value of ΔHa is obtained from literature⁷. The values of k'2 and k'1 are obtained from the slopes and intercepts, respectively. These values are reported in Table 2. The activation parameters are reported in Table 3.

Fig. 1. Plot of kobs · {Ka + [H⁺]}/[H⁺] vs [H⁺]⁻¹ for the reaction of Ni^{II} with DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF k₁ AND k₂ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	k ₁ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ⁻⁴ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
25	0	2.49
30	8	2.65
35	7	3.07
40	12	3.43

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS
CORRESPONDING TO k_1 AND k_2

$\Delta H_1^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta E_1^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H_2^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta E_2^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_2^\ddagger$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
25.42	25.74	23.48	2.20	2.44	-7.64

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (G.C.S. and J.P.) are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Senior Research Fellowships.

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Physicochemical and Catalytic Studies of some Molybdates†

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Manuscript received 7 January 1986, revised 18 March 1987,
accepted 23 July 1987

MOLYBDATES have been very popular as catalysts for oxidation and dehydrogenation reactions^{1,2}.

Though some of these have been used as catalysts in ammoxidation³, and a few others in the oxidation of methyl alcohol⁴, their effectiveness in the oxidation of CO has not been tested so far. In the present work, five molybdates have been investigated for their catalytic activities for CO oxidation and an attempt has been made to correlate the increasing order of activation energies with the labilisation of the double bonds.

Experimental

Molybdates of Cu, Co, Bi, Ni and Ag were prepared by mixing stoichiometric amounts of oxides, carbonates or nitrates of the above metals with ammonium molybdate, dissolving the mixture in concentrated nitric acid, evaporating the solution to dryness and calcining the intimate mixture at around 600° for 12 h.

† Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists 1985, at Raipur.

X-Ray diffraction patterns of the samples were taken in a Philips X-ray diffractometer. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

CO was produced by treating oxalic acid with concentrated H₂SO₄. It was passed through purifying towers and via a flow meter to a mixer. The purifying train consisted of towers containing pellets of sodium hydroxide and active charcoal powder, respectively. Air was fed from cylinders through the purifying towers to the mixer. The mixer was then passed through the catalyst bed in a reactor surrounded by a furnace. The collecting unit consisted of standard baryta solution. The CO₂ formed was estimated by the residual method.

Results and Discussion

The three most intense lines in the X-ray diffraction pattern of each of the molybdates as given in the ASTM powder diffraction file were observed in the patterns obtained in the present work also. The infrared spectra (1 000–600 cm⁻¹ range) the samples are given in Fig. 1.

X-Ray diffraction patterns show that molybdates have been formed completely in all the cases. Infrared spectral data (Table 1) show an interesting trend. For transition metal oxides the ir band due to the presence of metal oxygen double bond occurs around 1 000 cm⁻¹. For Mo—O double bond in MoO₃, the band occurs at 985 cm⁻¹. In these transition metal oxides, the most reactive oxygen atom is the one that is linked to the metal by a double bond. If the oxides containing a metal-oxygen double bond (e.g. MoO₃) is mixed with a second metal oxide, this ir band gets shifted to the lower frequency side⁵ due to labilisation of the double bond, i.e. weakening of the bond. The decreasing order of wave numbers corresponding $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ among the molybdates investigated is found to be MoO₃ > Co > Ni > Cu > Bi > Ag. Interestingly, the increasing order of activation energies is fairly the same as the above, Co < Ni < Cu < Bi < Ag. In general, a larger departure from the 985 cm⁻¹ value denotes a weaker Mo=O bond. However, this weakening of bond can have any perceptible effect on the catalytic behaviour of the substance only if the mechanism of oxidation involves lattice oxygen participation, i.e. participation of oxide in the oxidation. If on the other hand, the mechanism consists of adsorption of gaseous O₂ or CO, the labilisation of the metal-oxygen bond need not result in a decrease in activation energy⁶. In the present work, the increase in activation energy, E_a (Table 1) for CO oxidation parallels increase in ease of labilisation of M=O bond. Since the value of E_a for the reaction does not decrease with the weakening of the M=O bond, the lattice participation may be ruled out unlike the case of other reactions such as the oxidation of methanol by molybdates⁷. It is highly likely that CO interacts with Mo^{VI} rather than with the other metal ion in